

Reflection Of The Idea Of Respect And Protection Of Nature In The Avesto Work

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Abstract: *The article scientifically substantiates the ideas of respect and protection of nature and animal protection in the work "Avesta". The Zoroastrian religion, which is an important component of the religious heritage of our ancestors, and its sacred book "Avesta" occupy a huge place and significance in the history of our country and people. The Avesta widely covers such issues as philosophy, politics, morality, law, everyday life, way of life, conservation of land, water, flora and fauna, environment, raising children, kindness, tolerance, spirituality, and education.*

Keywords — nature, man, animal, plant world, values, good thought, good word, good deed, moral perfection, spiritual maturity, existence.

INTRODUCTION

Today, an objective study of our history of Uzbekistan has risen to the level of state policy. The Uzbek people are one of the peoples who have made a worthy contribution to the history of world culture. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "the study of our rich heritage, which represents the priceless values of our people and the rich experience of statehood" [1, p. 5] is a requirement of the time.

In fact, our cultural, historical and religious heritage, which for centuries has been the spiritual and moral source of our national spirit and identity, is the Avesta. It would be more correct to say that the rare book of our ancestors is a collection of spiritual and moral views on the implementation of national identity. In the Avesta, the issues of moral improvement and educational maturity of a person through "good intentions, good words and good deeds" are put in the foreground. Having its own socio-philosophical content, it serves as an important factor in the realization of the national identity of our people.

Zarathustra's words: "I salute a good intention, a good word and a good deed!" Among intentions, words and deeds, I choose good intentions, good words and good deeds. I will turn away from all evil thoughts, evil words and evil deeds" [2, p. 90-111], we believe that it should be emphasized that the wise words of our people today have great educational significance in understanding the national identity of our people.

It means a lot that the Avesta shows the integrity and unity of being, the harmony of human life with nature in close connection with the spiritual world of man.

"Avesta" describes the creation of the world, the development of man as a nation, the fight against the forces of evil and destruction in the name of goodness and creativity, dreams of freedom, freedom and development. "Avesta", as an ancient monument of our people, with its creative ideas, is an important factor in the spiritual growth and development of modern people, the preservation of their identity and national identity. In the Avesta there is an opinion that "punishment in hell for those who sinned before clean water and burning fire is worse than all the torments of this world" [2, p. 122]. The ideas of spiritual purity embody the way of life, traditions and spiritual experience of the Uzbek people and today help our people preserve their national mentality, identity, and deepen their understanding of their national identity.

According to scholars who have conducted research on Zoroastrianism, Zoroastrianism is a religion with deep roots, much of which is associated with older beliefs and remnants of ancient human lifestyles. Since Zoroastrianism is the oldest systematized religion of mankind, the primitive religious and philosophical attitude towards the world in it radically changes and acquires a clear spiritual orientation thanks to the reform and systematization of religion carried out by Zoroastrianism. As Professor G.T. Makhmudova correctly wrote, "Zoroastrians generalize various aspects of religious consciousness in the image of the creator of the universe - the single god Ahura Mazda. Thanks to this activity, Zarathustra appears before our eyes as a great reformer, philosopher and sage, who created the possibility of the religious and philosophical rise of humanity, expansion and deepening of the process of knowledge of the Universe" [3, p. 40].

The Avesta sanctifies soil, air, and water, considered as the material basis of the world. As Professor I. Khojamurodov notes: “Our ancestors treated nature with care and cherished it like the apple of their eye. Soil, water, air, fire were sanctified and revered” [4, p. 8].

Uzbek scientists (A. Askarov, A. Sagdullaev, E. Rtveldze, I. Dzhabborov, M. Ishakov, G. Makhmudova, etc.) note that the most ancient parts of the Avesta are reflected in the religion and way of life of the peoples of Bactria, Fergana, Greater Khorezm, Margyona and Sogdians proved this. Archaeological and linguistic research, some traditions and rituals that have been preserved among our people for thousands of years, leave no doubt that Khorezm is the birthplace of the Zoroastrian religion, and it is gratifying that the correctness of this opinion is supported by the majority of researchers conducting research on Zoroastrianism.

The philosophy of Zoroastrianism emphasizes that evil is an extremely negative action aimed at splitting society, destroying human relationships between people, and mercilessly criticizes ignorance. Academician A. Askarov rightly writes: “This religious view is widespread among the sedentary population belonging to the culture of irrigated agriculture. Because in the philosophy of Zoroastrianism the four elements of nature are sanctified: the sun (fire), earth (fertile soil), water - as the source of human life force, they give life to society; air, as a unique source of human health, provides spiritual and physical refreshment” [5, p. 544].

Forming a sense of responsibility in the younger generation not only for their lives, family members, country and nation, but also for the environment, the entire earth and all of humanity is the most important issue of the modern education system. It is not enough to educate a person only about the environment, about the rules of etiquette and morality. It is necessary to develop willpower, a sense of responsibility, to instill in the heart love for the environment, work, profession, science, other people, to achieve the birth of great goals in the language [6, p. 9]. For example, we must admit that it would be extremely naive to think that a person who reads books about the Fatherland or legal consciousness will immediately appreciate the Fatherland or not betray Justice. In order for the symbols of the Motherland, Nation and Justice to become permanent spiritual values in the soul, it is necessary for each person to try to follow the example of others, to be wise in this regard and to have love for them in his heart. This can be achieved in different ways, by different means, first of all, with a sincere (from the heart) and consistent approach to educating the younger generation, and tireless research.

Zoroastrianism deals with the phenomena of good and evil. If Ahura Mazda builds his land (country) on the basis of good, then Anhra Manu (Ahriman) builds the foundation of evil [7, p. 57-58]. In Anna, therefore, an eternal struggle arises between good and evil, light and darkness, life and death:

“The second land and beautiful land created by me - Ahura Mazda - was the land of Sogd.

After this, Ahriman came, whose entire existence was mixed with death, and created Skayatya, who belonged to the

family of Hrafstras. He spread the seed of death throughout the entire flock...” (“Vandidod”, 1-fargard, paragraph 5).

Ahura Mazda, the patron of all goodness, beauty and kindness, is supported by six forces of light. Concepts such as “Eternal Good”, “Good Thought”, “Good Order”, “Appropriate Power”, “Divine Submission”, “Health”, “Eternity” have their deities who sow the seeds of good around Ahura Mazda. Natural phenomena and various concepts associated with good acquired real meaning and humanized images were imagined. Cattle, fire, iron, thunder, clouds, stars, earth, water and plants had their own gods. For example, Mithra was considered the god of light, truth and purity.

Angra Manu, the god of evil and pleasure, also has his own spirits and powers. Angra Manu is trying to harm Ahura Mazda as much as possible and drive him out of the universe. He is the personification of lies, fraud, hypocrisy, ignorance and hypocrisy, and he is helped by giants. In particular, six giants are known: Apa Manna, personifying “evil thoughts”, Tuarvi and Zariklar, giants of “withering” and “death”.

If Ahura Mazda creates good and beautiful things, Anhra Manu creates bad and ugly things.

The struggle is manifested in the eternal and eternal discord between Ahura Mazda and Anhra Manu in religion, light and darkness in nature, life and death in existence, good and evil in morality, beauty and ugliness in the world of sophistication.

Ahura Mazda is the essence of all light, goodness and justice, and Anhra Manu is the sower of darkness, oppression, ugliness and injustice. One is a symbol of happiness and joy, and the other is a symbol of ignorance.

If these primitive souls are twins, then they are opposite to each other in their thoughts, words and actions. They are distinguished not by good and bad qualities, but by their sins.

When these two spirits were born, they created life and death; In the future life, let the cunning soul be given to sinners, and the virtuous soul to the righteous.

Those who could not distinguish them ran to the giants and fell into the trap of a cunning spirit who met the god of wrath to torment people with diseases.

When will these ignorant people be punished? When will lies leave you from your kingdom and truth will find you black?

And now the day of the cunning soul ends. All virtues - the soul - will gather in the beautiful abode of Mazda and Haqqaniyat and will be able to live happily”

[8, p. 174].

The spirit of good, described in the Avesta, is creativity, the power of creation, and the spirit of evil leads to destruction and decay. Good is a symbol of life, filling the earth with people, useful animals and plants, illuminating a person’s life with health, strength, happiness and joy, hope and confidence, the beauty and nobility of nature, and the abundance of hair. Evil

is the result of drought and famine, destruction of molar, diseases and disasters, physical and mental disorders.

During this struggle, lies and violence, darkness and despair, injustice and fraud sometimes prevail, but the bright forces of Ahura Mazda will finally defeat Anhra Manu, and the light will glorify goodness, beauty and joy in the world [9, p. 24].

According to the teachings of the Avesta, the Universe is built on the basis of the struggle of opposites: light and darkness in physical things, life and death in living nature, good and evil in the spiritual world and the struggle of fair laws. and lawlessness in public life. Ahura Mazda, the leader of the forces of light and goodness, does good, Ahriman, the spirit of evil, fights it and leads people to bad deeds and paths. A man of faith is always on the side of good. In this struggle, faith is expressed in the victory of light over darkness and good over evil.

Ahura Mazda encourages people to develop the habit of living in harmony with each other, to strive to abstain from selfishness, envy, greed, ambition and lawless acts. They say that keeping your word, being faithful to it, following contracts in trade, paying debts on time, being free from deception and betrayal are signs of faith. A believer is a perfect person who knows how to avoid theft and robbery, looking at other people's wealth, self-betrayal, that is, from actions that contradict his faith. Take care of your soul more than your body, that is, if your spiritual world is pure in the first place, then your material life will be perfect, says the Avesta.

Labor is extremely glorified in the Avesta. He considers work a source of goodness and material pleasure. They say that to be generous, a person must first work hard and create gifts with his own hands.

The Avesta says: "Whoever sows grain, sows the seed of piety, he cultivates the faith of devotion to Mazda, nourishes faith...". Following this is equivalent to praying ten thousand times and making hundreds of sacrifices. It is believed that planting crops and working is the elimination of evil. "When grain sprouts from the ground," it is said in the "Avesta," "giants tremble; when they reap grain, the giants groan and cry; when grain is threshed into flour, they die..." Labor is glorified.

The basis of Zoroastrian ethics is good thoughts, good words and good deeds.

Dobrye myshlenie oznachaet dobrotu k blizkim, gotovnost pomoch v nujde i odnosti, vsegda byt gotovym active borotsya za schaste i blagopoluchie lyudey, jit v soglasii so vsemi i t. d.

Dobrye slova – eto sderjat obeshchanie, sderjat svoe slovo, byt chestnym v delakh, vovremya vyplachivat dolgi, ne vorovat i grabit, vozderjivatsya ot korruptsii i t. d.

When I talk about good deeds, I have to follow all positive instructions, which are written in good words and good thoughts, and in my behavior.

Zoroastrian morality strictly prohibits cruelty to animals. Beating and torturing animals is considered a sin. Calls on

people to take care of useful animals, feed them on time, and protect them from predators.

Conclusion. Particular attention is paid to cleanliness in Avesta. A person who took water from a puddle in a dirty jug without washing it was punished with five lashes. Bathing and cleansing in the living room is strictly prohibited. Particular attention was paid to the purity and purity of the offspring, the presence of relatives and brothers and sisters was strictly controlled and condemned. Modern medical science has fully established that godlike relationships between brothers and close relatives negatively affect the healthy, fulfilling birth of the next generation. And the fact that our ancestors have already determined this will amaze modern people. In addition, in matters of marriage of close people there are spiritual aspects that the human heart should not allow.

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